

Capturing Protein Dynamics and Its Determinants Using Explainable Artificial Intelligence

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Molecular dynamics (MD), relying on physical laws of motion, predicts the movement of atoms and molecules over time, playing a key role in understanding the physical properties of materials and biological systems like proteins, DNA, and small molecules. However, the complexity of these systems makes it difficult to analyze their behavior using traditional methods alone such as visual inspection or unsupervised clustering. Machine learning (ML) and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) offer powerful tools for tackling this challenge by enabling the analysis of large, complex datasets, uncovering patterns and relationships, and making predictions [1]. XAI provides a transparent and interpretable framework for understanding ML model outputs, which is especially valuable in scientific research. Methods like layer-wise relevance propagation (LRP) help researchers to identify the most influential input features driving predictions made on a model, offering insights into the underlying factors affecting the results. This study aims to determine whether XAI can capture the dynamic determinants of a selected group of luciferases, RLuc8, AncFT, and Anc^{HLD-RLuc}, and to compare these findings with experimental results. We are developing an XAI-based method leveraging MD data and autoencoder architecture. Identifying key dynamic regions provides insights that could be leveraged for enzyme design and optimization, facilitating rational engineering strategies. Notably, the method highlights the L9- α 4- α 5' fragment as a critical region for dynamics prediction, aligning with previous experimental and computational findings that emphasize its importance in the structural behavior of these proteins [2].

[1] Kouba P et al. "Machine learning-guided protein engineering." ACS Catalysis 13.21(2023):13863-95.

[2] Schenk Mayerova et al. "Engineering the protein dynamics of an ancestral luciferase." Nature Communications 12.1(2021):3616.

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